

Ownership Structure and Dividend Policy of Listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria

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Abstract: This study examines the impact of ownership structure on dividend policy of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria from 2009 to 2019. It explores the impact of different investor types on dividend policy of deposit money banks. Dividend policy is measured as dividend yield. As a result, the study predicts dividend behaviour based on ownership structure which is useful since ownership structure has been changing over time. Questions arise whether or not dividend should be paid and to what extent should dividend be paid? The sample is made up of 11 banks. Secondary data were collected from the annual reports of the banks. Robust Tobit Regression was employed in analysing the data. The findings of the study showed that institutional shareholdings, ownership concentration and foreign shareholdings have positive and significant impacts, while managerial shareholdings have negative and significant impact on dividend policy. It was concluded that managerial shareholding will discourage the policy of dividend payment of deposit money banks listed in Nigeria while institutional shareholdings improves the policy of paying dividend in deposit money banks listed in Nigeria. The recommendation of the study among others is that investors in listed DMBs in Nigeria seeking for capital gain to watch out firms with more directors ownership. They may invest in such companies that offer more short-term benefits or gains in capital from the perspective of the investor and also if investors are looking for high short-term dividends, they ought to put into consideration companies who have recently make payment for dividends and look after companies with large institutional investors, because they are more dividend payable. Limitation of the study shows the inability to generalize results to other sectors.

Keywords: Dividend policy, ownership structure, director ownership, institutional ownership

1. Introduction

Policies set aside for dividend payment is essential to the organization. Dividend is the distribution of profits to shareholders and undistributed profits is retained in the business as re-investment by the organization for a given financial year as agreed by the board; and approve by the shareholders at the AGM of the corporation (Hasnain et al., 2011). Dividend payment is the quantity of earned profit to be retained and the quantity of earned profit to be distributed as dividend (Hosseini, 2012). One of the most maximum vital components of corporate coverage is the dividend charge coverage and the decision to pay or no longer pay dividends throughout a financial year (Idris, 2016). Ownership structure has to do with the composition of a company's ordinary shareholding which they are, concentrated share ownership foreign, institutional, and government.

The banking industry play a vital role in ownership structure to shareholders. Most literature carried out in the banking industry in Nigeria was centered on different variables like capital adequacy, credit risk, loan loss provision, and impact of capital market on banks performance. This work tends to analyse the trend of how dividend policy affects diverse ownership structure in the listed Nigeria deposit money banks.

Most of the studies fail to capture all the variables of ownership structure, just a few was selected and used, with a limited number of years .Studies have focused on firms of industrialize countries,we are looking at variables such as director's proportion ownership, foreign share ownership, ownership concentration, and institutional share ownership. Closely related to this research is the research work of (Idris & Shuaibu, 2016) where they used Tobit regression technique using four proxies which are directors shareholdings, institutional, foreign and ownership concentration, for the period of five years 2010-2014. This studies sampled ten (10) out of seventeen (17) listed deposit bank in Nigeria.This study examine director's share ownership, foreign share ownership, ownership concentration and institutional share ownership these variables influence dividend policy,and its covers a period of eleven (11) years (2009-2019).The dependent variable is the deposit money bank dividend policy which is calculated has dividend yield (DY) Ownership structure which is determine by director's share ownership, foreign share ownership, ownership concentration and institutional share ownership is the study independent variable,the study focuses on only on a small number of ownership structure variables and just a variable of dividend policy, so to the dynamism of other variables are not in focus due to unavailability and limitation of data.

However, despite these limitations, the study could be used to support the justification for the impact of ownership structure and dividend policy of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. As a result, the following particular goals are to: determine the impact of director's shareholding, institutional shareholding on dividend policy, ownership concentration on dividend policy and foreign ownership on divided policy of banks.

The following hypotheses have been formulated.

H0₁: Directors shareholdings have no significant impact on dividend policy of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.

H0₂: Institutional shareholdings have no significant impact on dividend policy of listed deposit money banks Nigeria.

H0₃: Ownership concentration has no significant impact on dividend policy of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.

H0₄: Foreign shareholdings has no significant impact on dividend policy of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.

2. Literature Review

Ownership structure involves the relationship that exists between groups of individuals that constitute or make up owners of a company. A company ownership can take several different forms. As a result there are various forms of ownership,including management ownership, government, family, foreign, associate and ownership according to Okpanachi and Mohammed (2018) for the purpose of this study, the most common shareholding type will be considered which include ownership concentration, Director's share ownership, institution share ownership and foreign share ownership.

Directors' ownership could be defined as a percentage of shares held by independent non-executive Directors, executive Directors and non-independent non-executive Directors' Hashim (2008). According to Che (2003) director's ownership may be divided into two insider ownership and outsider ownership. Insider ownership refers to the percentage of share owned by insider board members, including executive directors and non-independent non-executive directors. As in previous research, the ratio of shares held and their close families is used to determine directors' ownership (Gill & Obradovich 2013; Short et al., 2002). Directors' ownership is the share ownership directly and indirectly by board of directors' members.

Institutional shareholding refers to a larger contribution from a group of institutions than an investor. Hoseinbeglou et al. (2003) calculate the number of companies owned by major investing institutions (those who hold more than 5% of a company's stock). Institutional investors, according to Koh (2003), are major shareholders such as insurance companies, banks, pension funds, and financial institutions firms associated with the mentioned categories of institutions. Institutional ownership, as described by Hashim (2008), is the proportion of shares held by the largest corporate investors to the total number of shares issued. Institutional ownership refers to the ownership of shares by large shareholders which have more leverage than those controlled by insurance companies, banks, mutual funds, and other financial institutions.

Concentrated ownership is also known as block-shareholding indicating shareholders with 5% and above of the equity shares of a company Mitton (2004). The measurement of Concentrated ownership is done using the percentage of ownership of the main shareholders (as many shareholders as possible are added up together) with more than 5% of total shares, this has been used by previous researchers such as Habibi et al. (2012). According to Mirzaei (2016), there are two theories related to Ownership Concentration and Dividend coverage. The first theory is concerned about firms with fewer foreign stockholders and a lower percentage of stockholders do not tend to distribute profit. Since the expense of agency is higher when the number of foreign stockholders is higher. The second hypothesis proposed that paying the distributive profit serves as a substitute for supervision.

Individuals who are not residents of a nation or business organization whose headquarters are not in that country owning or controlling a company or natural resource. Generally, foreign ownership occurs when multinational companies with operations in several countries make long-term investments in a foreign country, typically in the form of foreign direct investment. Foreign ownership may also occur when a foreign person purchases a domestic property. An Indian businessman purchasing a home in Hong Kong is an example.

Dividend yield measures the return as in the form of dividend and price appreciation and the risk associated with the investment in stock. The dividend yield calculates the stock's dividend and price changes, as well as the stock's investment risk. The dividend yield ratio is influenced by external variables (Warren et al., 2011). As a measure of the dividend policy, the study used dividend yields. The study will consider two key theories that inform the study that includes agency theory, and Signaling theory. An agency relationship exists when an independent person appointed by the principal is mandated to act, make decisions and carry responsibilities on their behalf. The cost of an agency emerges as a result of the managers' and owners' competing interests. Dividend payment, according to Jensen (1986), can trigger conflicts between managers and shareholders because managers prefer to keep capital rather than pay dividends. Managers

are interested in learning about their companies' growth plans because it will give them more leverage to influence them.

Signaling theory proposes that agents send and relay information to the principal in order to be seen as trustworthy in their dealings. Managers are in the forefront regarding issues of the company than investors, but they are still hesitant to provide shareholders with clear information. As a result, the dividend strategy can be used for both details and guideline. Dividend policy, according to (Miller & Rock, 1985) is important because it serves as a basis to communicate information to shareholders about the organization value. Institutional shareholders, in addition to dividends, can be seen as more effective signaling since they have a greater influence in monitoring the firm's results.

According to the empirical literature many researchers attempt to examine the ownership structure and dividend policy. Prior studies also found out that the quality of ownership structure is highly associated and influence by certain variables of dividend policy. Lacey et al. (2013) reported in the same sense that foreigners prefer investments in developing markets companies when there is a high dividend incentive for the period 2009-2013. Le and Le (2017) examined the correlation between the identities and levels of shareholdings, as well as the cash dividend policy of 180 companies listed on the Vietnam stock exchange markets. The findings revealed that companies with international investors as major shareholders had a higher dividend payout than companies with local investors as major shareholders. The findings also revealed that decrease in the dividend yield, result to the increase in the percentage held by the largest shareholders. Foreign investors prefer higher dividend payments in a developing economies setting, Le & Le (2017), since they have no substantial knowledge about the firm's success and market stability.

Idris and Hussaini (2016) carried a research from 2010 to 2014 on how dividend policy influences forms of ownership structure. Data from a focus group Tobit regression was used as the study's analysis method. Using a sample of ten of Nigeria's fourteen listed deposit money banks. The findings indicate that managerial ownership and ownership concentration are likely to have a substantial negative effect on the dividend policies of Nigeria's publicly traded deposit money banks. Though institution proportion has a possibly substantial positive effect on dividend of Nigeria's deposit money banks.

Abdul-azeez (2016) looked at the consequence of ownership structure on the dividend policy of Srilanka quoted companies from 2006 to 2014. The study used multiple regression technique of data analysis, using a panel data from the annual reports and accounts of the sampled listed companies to conduct data analysis. The study findings indicate that institutional ownership has a negative but minor sequel on the dividend payment policies of the companies studied. The study considers only institutional ownership instead of considering other factors.

Masoyi et al. (2016) used secondary data from the annual report to analyze how different owners reacts to dividend policy. They sample 13 deposit banks in Nigeria, over a five-year financial statement and accounts (2009-2013). The data collected used OLS multiple regression methodology, the research discovered that institutional shareholding and ownership concentration had a substantial significant effect during the study era. Directors' shareholding,

has no substantial change on dividend of deposit banks in Nigeria, according to the report. The research work should have considered more than five-year period.

Mirzaei (2016) looked at how the ownership structure and dividend policy interact. He bases his research on a sample of 88 companies that were listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange between 2004 and 2009. The findings of this study show that institutional ownership and dividend policy have a strong negative relationship. However, Mirzaei (2016) could not obtain a significant relationship between managerial ownership and dividend payment. The study also concludes that the variable of ownership concentration and dividend policy have a positive and substantive relationship. The research in this field did not conduct rigorous tests to improve the validity and reliability of statistical inferences drawn from the studies. However, this study intends to analyse its variables using descriptive statistics and regression analysis with STATA (version 13) package and to carry out multicollinearity, heteroskedasticity tests among others. This study opposes the view of Okpanachi et al. (2018) in their study on ownership structure and dividend policy of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. A generalized least square regression model was used, they found that managerial shareholdings strongly and positively affect dividend policy.

The ownership structure and dividend policy were investigated by Mehrani, et al. (2011). The results indicate that there is a negative relationship between institutional ownership and dividend payout, but a positive relationship between concentrated ownership and dividend payment, for a span of eight years (8) from 2000 to 2007. These results support Thanatawee's stance (2014). However, on the contrary Ullah et al. (2012), Miko and Kamaradin (2015) are of the opinion that there is a positive relationship between institutional ownership and dividend policy.

3. Methodology

Ex-post factor research design was adopted to examine ownership structure on dividend policy of the listed deposit money banks in Nigeria for the period of eleven (11) years 2009-2019. The data was sourced from annual reports and accounts published by the banks. The population consists 14 deposit money banks listed in Stock Exchange (NSE) (now Nigerian Exchange Group) as at December 2019. The justification for the population is due to the availability of data from the NSE site. The study conducted descriptive analysis to understand the nature of the data. The study employed Tobit regression approach. Where the dependent variable is characterized by a censored value, Tobit regression was used (Anh & Tuan, 2019). The data was analyzed with the aid of STATA statistical software.

The independent proxies of the study consist of four type of ownership structure that is Director's ownership (DSO), Institutional ownership (ISO), Foreign Ownership (FO), Firm Size (FS) and Ownership concentrated (OC). The choice of the variables and their measurement are guided by the literature reviewed and are in line with the work of Dandago et al. (2015), Miko (2015), Ullah (2012). Hence, the model is mathematically expressed as:

$$DPY_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 DSO_{it} + \beta_2 ISO_{it} + \beta_3 OC_{it} + \beta_4 FSO_{it} + \beta_4 FS_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Whereas:

DY_{it} = is the dependent variable representing dividend yield

DSO_{it} = Directors' share ownership of company I in year t

ISO_{it} = Institutional share ownership of company

OC_{it} = Ownership concentration of company

FSO_{it} = Foreign share ownership of company

FS_{it} = Firm size of company i in t

α = the intercept element

ϵ_{it} = Error term

Table 1

Variable	Definition	Measurement	Source
DY	Dividend Yield	Annual dividend per share by the price per share	Dandago et al.(2015),
DSO	Directors' Share Ownership	shares held by the Directors' to the total ordinary share capital	Ullah,(2012) Short (2000) Miko (2015),
ISO	Institutional Share Ownership	shares held by corporate bodies over total ordinary share capital	Dandago et al. (2015), Ullah (2012)
OC	Ownership Concentration	Proportion of 5percent equity share to total ordinary share capital	Murtaza & Azam, (2019)
FSO	Foreign Ownership	Capital inflows from one country to another	Chen et al. (2005), Laporta et al. (1999)
FS	Firm Size	Natural Log of total assets	Truong &Heaney (2007).

4. Results

The section concludes by testing the study's hypotheses and discussing the key findings and policy implication of their results. The descriptive statistics of the explained and the explanatory variables were presented in Table 1.

Table 2

Normality Test of Data

Variables	OBS	Pr (Skewness)	Pr (Kurtosis)	adj chi2(2)	Prob>chi2
DY	121	0.000	0.0000	.	0.000
DSO	121	0.000	0.007	30.52	0.000
ISO	121	0.005	0.264	8.27	0.016
OC	121	0.087	0.358	6.83	0.033
FSO	121	0.000	.422	19.15.	0.000
FSZ	121	0.000	0.000	29.08	0.000

Source:stata 13 output,2021

Note. * $p < 0.05$ significance level

The study tested for normality of the data which reveals the skewness, Kurtosis and Joint value (Jacque Bera value). Table 4 reveals that all the variables fails the normality test. The table indicate that the individual P-value of all the variables is less than 5% demonstrating that the data are not normally distributed. To remedy for this problem, a robust standard error regression approach was employed.

Multicollinearity Test

For the purpose of multicollinearity, the study used variance inflation factor (VIF). Multicollinearity deals with the association between the independent variables. Since VIF cannot be estimated directly through Tobit regression, the study employed the COLLIN command to establish the collinearity among the predictors.

Table 3

Multicollinearity Test

	Model	
Variables	VIF	Tolerance Value
DSO	1.23	0.81
ISO	1.45	0.69
OC	1.61	0.62
FSO	1.13	0.89
FSZ	1.56	0.64

Stata 13 Output (2021)

Another test conducted is test for multicollinearity. It is assumed that the explanatory proxies should not strongly correlate. Hair et al., (2010) state that, VIF above 4 and tolerance value below 0.20 is a pointer of multicollinearity presence. The results from Table 5 show that no harmful interrelation between the independent variables since the lowest tolerance value (TV) is 0.62 while the highest variance inflation factor (VIF) is 1.61

Heteroskedasticity

Table 4

Heteroskedasticity Test

	chi2	Prob > chi2
Cameron & Trivedi's decomposition Test	34.55	0.026

Note. * p<0.05 significance level

Stata Output (2021)

Tobit regression assumes homoscedasticity of the residual (i.e., constant error variance or no heteroscedasticity). Although the researcher was not able to get a direct for heteroscedasticity in Tobit regression, for this study, heteroscedasticity test was conducted. The assumption of the null hypothesis is that the error variance is alike across the values of the independent variables at 5% decision level. The test reveal that there is problem of heteroscedasticity with the model as there P-value is (0.026) which is less than 5% level of significance. Therefore, a robust standard error Regression will be use to correct the issue.

Model specification Error

Tobit model assumes well specification and adequacy of model. This assumption was check using linktest for Tobit Regression.

Table 5

Model specification error test

<i>Linktest</i>	Chi2/hatsq	Prob > chi2
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Stata 13 Output, 2021

Model specification error test was conducted to check if the model is adequately fit (Neyman, 2018). According to Chen et al. (2009) if model is correctly specified, we may not find further predictors that is significant except by chance. The study used Linktest to check for model specification error. The model has a null hypothesis and there is no model specification error variable at 5percent level of significance. The table reveals that the linktest indicate a p-value of 0.798 which insignificantly indicated that model is well specified.

Information Criteria and likelihood ratio

The choice arises base on two information criteria (Akaike information criterion (AIC) and Bayesian facts criterion (BIC) for the two regression. the version with the lowest AIC and BIC is the maximum suitable for the study.

Table 6*Information Criteria and Likelihood ratio Rho Test***Information Criteria**

Model	AIC	BIC
Pooled Tobit model	33.46	55.82
Random Tobit Model	57.75	77.31

Stata 13 Output (2021)

Table 6 shows that the pooled Tobit regression has an Akaike information criterion (33.46) and Bayesian facts criterion (55.82) while the random effect model has an AIC (57.75) and BIC (77.31). it shows that the Tobit regression is more suitable. The study employed robust standard error Tobit regression in other to take care of any heteroskedacity issue and non-normality of the data.

Presentation of Estimation Results

Table 7 presents the regression results for robust Tobit regression.

Table 7*Robust Pooled Tobit Model*

Variables	Coefficients	Std Error	T-Value	P-value
DSO	-0.02	0.01	-2.19	0.030*
ISO	0.12	0.02	5.47	0.000*
OC	0.10	0.04	2.71	0.008*
FSO	0.09	0.02	4.32	0.000*
FSZ	0.05	0.01	3.56	0.001*
CONST	-0.09	0.32	-0.29	0.775
Pseudo R2	0.668			
F-stat	15.02			0.000
No of Observation	121			
No of group	11			

Stata 13 output, 2021

Note: * p<0.05 significance level

Table 7 revealed the result of the robust Tobit regression to correct for the violation of non-normality of residual and heteroscedastic assumption. Table 7 revealed an R² of 0.668. This showed that the individual ownership structure variables and the control variable (firm size) are capable of providing an explanation for modifications in the dividend policy of quoted DMBs in

Nigeria at 66.8%. Others (33.2%) are accounted for variables not included in the study. The F-statistics of the model indicates a significant joint effect of the variables on dividend policy measured by dividend yield. This also shows that the study model is fit ($P < 0.000$).

The formulated hypotheses of the study are tested below using information from table 7

H₀₁: Director's shareholdings have a negative significant.

Table 7 reveals that directors' shareholdings have a p-value of 0.030 which is statistically significant at 5% level. It suggests that directors' shareholdings has significant impact on dividend policy. Hence the null hypothesis (H₀₁) is rejected.

H₀₂: Institutional shareholdings have no significant impact.

Table 7 reveals that Institutional shareholdings has beta value of 0.12 ($P = 0.000$) is widespread at less than 5% level of importance. Thus, the study does not accept the null hypothesis (H₀₂).

H₀₃: Concentrated ownership have no impact on dividend policy on quoted banks in Nigeria:

From the results in Table 7, ownership concentration has a statistically significant P-value of 0.008 at less 5% level of significance. Therefore, the research rejects the null hypothesis (H₀₃), ownership concentration has no significance on DMBs.

H₀₄: Foreign shareholdings have no significant impact on dividend policy.

Table 7 shows that foreign shareholding has a p-value of 0.001 which is significant at less than 5% level of significance ($P = 0.001$). Thus, the research rejects the null hypothesis (H₀₄). The research found that institutional investors, foreign investors and concentrated ownership positive improve dividend payment rather quest for re-investment. policy makers and the board of directors have been provided with evidence on the important of dividend payment to these set of investors. This will guide the directors in ensuring that the firms pay dividend and to continue to attract foreign investment in Nigeria DMBs. It also provides evidence to policy makers and investors on the preference of capital gain rather than dividend payment by directors.

5. Conclusion

In relation with the findings in chapter four and the foregoing summary of the study, conclusion is as follows: From the model, it was found out that director ownership significantly reduces dividend yield of the sampled in the sector of Nigeria banks. Based on that, the study also concludes that director shareholding will discourage dividend payment policy. Secondly, the study found that institutional-shareholding by increasing dividend yield of the sampled banks, depicts the monitoring role of investors thus, fulfills the expectations of agency theory. The study, therefore, concludes that institutional shareholding improves the dividend policy. Thirdly, the results in the model shows that ownership concentration positively and significantly influences dividend yield in the sampled banks. This suggests that block investor (shareholders with up to 5% share interest in the sample firms) induce firms to pay dividend rather than focus in capital gain. Hence, the study concludes that the concentration of ownership will improves the dividend policy. Finally, the study discover that foreign shareholding has a positive and significant impact on dividend yield. Therefore, the study concludes that a foreign shareholding enhances the dividend policy.

The study recommends that investors in the listed DMBs in Nigeria seeking for capital gain to watch out firms with more directors ownership. They may invest in such companies that offer more short-term benefits or gains in capital from the perspective of the investor. The ownership structures should be taken into account by those investors interested in investing in DMBs when making investment decisions. For example, whenever investors are looking for high short-term

dividends, they ought to put into considerations companies that have recently paid dividends and look after companies with large institutional investors, because they are more dividend payable. The study recommends to CBN and FRCN not to discourage concentrated ownership as they assist in improving dividend decision. It is recommended that the directors board of the Nigeria listed DMBs, are to improve in their dividend payment policy so as to attract foreign investors. In appointing directors to the board, emphasis should be made on appointing those with the accurate knowledge in the field of accounting and finance. By so doing they actually possess the physical and mental stamina to carry out the active responsibilities and activities of the board, which monitoring to checkmate the discretionary behaviour of management requires.

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